

GENDER EQUALITY ISSUES IN THE WORLD AND UZBEKISTAN EXPERIENCE

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Annotation: In this article, issues of gender equality, the increasing role of women and girls in our society, a number of opportunities created for them, the education of women and girls are expressed in the example of the world and Uzbekistan.

Key words: gender, gender equality, women's rights, human dignity and dignity, freedom, interest.

Today, in the scientific literature, research and debate, the term "gender", associated with it, is widely used phrases such as "gender relations", "gender equality", "gender Culture", "gender Development", "gender sociology", "gender psychology". The next twenty years can be called the "era of gender exploration", and today's science is developing from the path of deepening. However, it also assumes generalization, analysis and synthesis. Artificial deepening of Gender relations, even if gender enriches research, does not serve progress, but, on the contrary, enhances gender stratification. Therefore, gender studies should be based on the goal of strengthening the relationship between the Sexes.

The human race is wounded, special attention is paid to the issues of male and Female Attitude, their place in society, family, gender equality. Even in our country, work on issues of gender equality deserves special recognition. In particular, a dialogue of leading women was organized among the Central Asian countries, in which Uzbekistan presided for the first time in 2021.

Today, gender equality is one of the most important areas of policy of the UN, PI, other international and regional organizations and structures, States. Because it is one of the basic requirements and necessary conditions for guaranteeing human dignity, freedoms and interests, ensuring the sustainable development of the global and states, establishing peace and tranquility. In this area, within the framework of the UN alone, dozens of international documents have been adopted, such as a number of international treaties, in particular the Universal Declaration of human rights, international pacts on Civil and political rights, economic, social and cultural rights, the convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women, the Beijing Declaration and the platform of action. They are characterized by the fact that gender embodies the principles of equality and justice, is interconnected, dictates and complements each other, and is viable.

In ensuring Gender equality, trends are manifested in the reflection of relevant issues in World constitutions, the adoption of "gender-sensitive constitutions". Of course, Uzbekistan is also stepping from this direction along with the world community.

In this regard, the Secretary General of the Inter-Parliamentary Union M. Chungong spoke on gender politics and constitutional reform in Uzbekistan, arguing that the adoption of a "Gender sensitive constitution" would serve to effectively protect women's freedoms, rights

and interests in the country, and that they would be discriminated against and that any violence against them would not be allowed"[2].

The study of World constitutionalism testifies to the inclusion of the principle of gender equality in constitutions as the first step towards the implementation of the principle of equality between women and men in accordance with international obligations. Consequently, in the preparation of the draft constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition, it is evidence of our opinion that the criteria for equal rights of citizens, responsibility to the law and justice in the obligation are also taken as the basis.

It is reflected in our head that human dignity is great, rights and interests are guaranteed. It is noteworthy that the draft constitution of the new edition provides for the inviolability of the honor and dignity of a person, that nothing can serve as a basis for their discrimination. For example, Article 42 strengthens the rights to work: "everyone has the right to work with decent labor, to freely choose a profession and type of activity, to work in favorable working conditions that meet the requirements of safety and hygiene, to receive a fair remuneration without any discrimination for their labor and in a way not less than the established minimum amount of The minimum amount of remuneration is determined taking into account the need to ensure a person's decent standard of living. It is forbidden to refuse to hire women because they are pregnant or have a child, to dismiss them and to reduce their wages".[5]

In addition, a number of decrees and projects are being developed to increase the activity of women and girls in society, providing them with wide opportunities. Chunonchi, in 2022 — 2026, a national program was developed to increase the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life.[PF-87.07.03.2022]. In accordance with the program, a number of conditions were created for their education, interest-free loans were allocated for the education of women in higher education musassas in the 7th term, payment contracts of women studying in the magistracy were covered at the expense of state budgets without the provision of repayment.

Both our prosperous life today and our bright future depend on women. If we want our people to agree with us, we must first create suitable living conditions for our humble mothers, sisters. If the mother agrees, the family agrees, and if the family agrees, the society agrees, " Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.[1]

In conclusion, it can be said that human honor and dignity are above all else, and I believe that the future of a country that knows, venerates, acts kindness to its women, encourages them to be progressive in any field will be great because, before making our children scientific, we aim to educate our women-girls in a way that is scientific and.

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